

FABRICATION OF LaInO₃ THIN FILMS BY PULSED LASER DEPOSITION

THESIS

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the Degree of

MASTER OF TECHNOLOGY

in

NANOTECHNOLOGY

By

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(Reg. No. 12MNT0034)

Under the Guidance and Supervision of

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SCHOOL OF ELECTRONICS ENGINEERING

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BONAFIDE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis titled "*Fabrication of LaInO₃ thin films by pulsed laser deposition*" that is being submitted by *Chaluvadi Sandeep Kumar (12MNT0034)*, is in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of **Master of Technology in Nanotechnology**, Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT University), Vellore, TN, is a record of bonafide work done under the guidance and supervision of Dr. Anjana Dogra and Dr. Gargi Raina. The contents of this thesis, in full or in parts, have neither been taken from any other source nor have been submitted to any other Institute or University for award of any degree or diploma and the same is certified.

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ABSTRACT

Lanthanum Indium Oxide (LaInO_3) is a rare-earth oxide perovskite known to exhibit luminescence under UV excitation in its bulk form. However till date no attempt has been made to fabricate its thin films. In the present work, our emphasis is on fabrication of thin films of LaInO_3 by using pulsed laser deposition technique.

LaInO_3 thin films from bulk target were prepared on TiO_2 terminated single crystal (001) orientated Strontium Titanate (SrTiO_3) substrate. Various films were prepared by varying temperature, oxygen pressure and substrates. The structural and morphological studies have been performed on the LaInO_3 bulk powder and thin films using X-ray diffraction (XRD), field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) technique. To verify its luminescent characteristics in thin films photoluminescence (PL) studies were carried out in detail in the spectrum range of 200-800 nm. The broad band blue luminescence is observed in the host lattice LaInO_3 . The origin of luminescence in the thin films is primarily attributed to the charge transfer transitions between oxygen and indium, inter ($d-f$) and intra ($f-f$) band transitions. Thin films deposited at low oxygen pressure (1×10^{-4} mbar) exhibits green luminescence due to oxygen deficiencies along with blue luminescence. Broadening of the PL emission in thin films is observed with reduction in size of the crystal owing to quantum confinement effects.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AFM	Atomic Force Microscopy
EDX	Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy
HF	Hydro Fluoric acid
HV	High vacuum
ITO	Indium Tin Oxide
KrF	Krypton Fluoride
LIO	Lanthanum Indium Oxide (LaInO_3)
Mbar	millibar (pressure unit)
MgO	Magnesium Oxide
NH_4F	Ammonium Fluoride
Nm	Nanometre
Ns	Nanosecond
PID	Proportional Integrator and Differentiator
PL	Photoluminescence
PLD	Pulsed Laser Deposition
PLE	Photoluminescence Excitation
PVA	Polyvinyl Alcohol
PVD	Physical Vapour Deposition
RHEED	Reflection High Energy Electron Diffraction
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cells
STO	Strontium Titanate (SrTiO_3)
UHV	Ultra high vacuum
UV	Ultraviolet

CHAPTER 1**INTRODUCTION****1.1 Introduction to oxides**

Complex oxide material properties are important to study as they will play a key role in future. They are required to understand the new functionalities and further miniaturization of integrated circuits, electronic devices in emerging market. Oxide deposition techniques gained interest in technological advancement as on other side the limits of standard silicon and III-V binary semiconductor technology are approaching in terms of miniaturization and high-k dielectrics [1]. Therefore, a large research effort has been committed in growing different complex oxide films and their structures. Oxides, on the other hand, may find suitable for many applications because they may exhibit unique properties like conductivity, piezoelectricity, dielectricity, transparency, phosphorescence, luminescent, optical non linearity, colossal magneto resistance (CMR) etc.

1.2 Introduction to perovskite

Most of the compounds with the general formula of ABX_3 have the perovskite structure. A perovskite structure is coined as any material with the same

Figure 1.1: The crystal structure of an ABO_3 perovskite with the origin centred at (a) B-site ion and (b) A-site ion.

type of crystal structure as $CaTiO_3$, as it was first found for mineral perovskite structure. The general formula for perovskite compounds is ABX_3 , where 'A' & 'B'

are two cations of different sizes and 'X' is an anion (generally oxygen) that bonds with both the cations 'A' & 'B'. In general, size of cation 'A' is larger than cation 'B'. The cation 'A' is either a monovalent, divalent or trivalent metal and cation 'B' is either a pentavalent, tetravalent or trivalent element respectively. In the perovskite type oxides, the 'A' cation is coordinated with twelve oxygen ions whereas the 'B' cation with six. In the ideal class, the perovskite structure is of cubic with space group belongs to Pm3m. On the other hand, most of the materials that are characterized as perovskites are not cubic due to the slight tilt or distortions of the oxygen octahedra surrounding the B-site ions. The BO₆ oxygen octahedra form a three-dimensional network, so that if the system is metallic, electrical conduction is three-dimensional along the BO₆ network. The most important advantage of the perovskite structure is that the BO₆ network remains stable for substitutions of the A-site cation. The ionic radii difference of cations play a critical role in determining the crystal structure in these ABO₃ compounds. It is given by tolerance factor 't'. When the value of t is almost 1, the system is cubic; while for the value t < 1, the lattice structure changes from cubic to rhombohedral and then to the orthorhombic GdFeO₃ type.

$$t = \frac{r_A + r_O}{\sqrt{2}(r_B + r_O)} \quad (1.1)$$

where r_A , r_B , r_O are the radii of the cation 'A³⁺', 'B³⁺', and anion 'X²⁻' (generally Oxygen) respectively and 't' is given as tolerance factor.

Table 1.1: Perovskite structure according to tolerance factor

't' range	Structure
$t \leq 0.96$	Orthorhombic structure
$0.96 \leq t \leq 1.06$	Cubic
$t \geq 1.06$	Hexagonal

Rare-earth oxides with perovskite structure have attracted researchers in the past years due to their potential applications in the field of semiconductor industry, electronics, telecommunication (dielectric resonators), environmental contaminant

(radioactive waste encapsulation), display devices like plasma panel displays (PPD); flat panel displays (FDP) and solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC). Their novel properties and applications in the field of luminescence attracted us to study the optical properties of complex oxides.

1.3 Literature review on photoluminescence

Recent advancements in display device technology has led to various types of displays such as field emission displays (FEDs), plasma panel displays (PDPs), electroluminescent (EL), photoluminescent (PL), vacuum fluorescent displays (VFDs) and light emitting diodes (LEDs). The phosphor required for each display device is different. Phosphors used in FED devices should have low excitation voltage (<1 kV), high brightness, high contrast ratio, longer life and high resistance to surface build-up charges. [2–4]. Although, many efficient sulfide-based phosphors such as $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ (red), $\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Tb}^{3+}$ (green), $\text{SrGa}_2\text{S}_4:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ (green), and $\text{ZnS}:\text{Ag}^+, \text{Cl}^-$ (blue), etc., have been explored [5, 6] as possible low voltage phosphors. But, these traditional sulfide based phosphors that are used in cathode ray tube (CRTs) were not suitable in current display technology. However, using the sulfide-based phosphors has disadvantages such as chemical instability, corrosion of the emitter cathode induced by sulfur-related contaminant gases and luminescence saturation at high excitation density. Corrosion at electrodes may lead to release of harmful sulfide based gases in the environment and fast degradation of devices when they are operated at high current densities. So the trend has been shifted towards emerging oxides that can replace sulfide based display devices. However, the oxide based phosphors such as $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ (red), $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Tb}^{3+}$ (green) and $\text{Y}_2\text{SiO}_5:\text{Ce}^{3+}$ (blue) that can exhibit luminescence and thought to replace sulfide based devices. But all these oxide phosphors are insulators (no intrinsic conductivity) and when they are excited by low voltage (<1kV) cathode ray, accumulation of surface charge problems occurs on the surface [6, 7]. This is not a desirable characteristic for luminescent devices. By considering above facts, there

was a search for the material that exhibits the above characteristics. Oxides are chemically and thermally stable and most of the oxides are insulators which may not prevent surface build-up charges when excited with low emission voltages. To overcome this effect, we need a material with an intrinsic conductivity. Therefore, semiconducting oxides that are well suitable and can replace the traditional sulfide based phosphors.

In last decade, when Kao *et al.*[8] and Baszczuk *et al.*[9] published reports on indium based alkaline earth metal oxide semiconductors like SrIn_2O_4 and CaIn_2O_4 that acts as a host lattices for luminescence. They have observed red emitting luminescence along with intrinsic broad-band emission when doped with Pr^{3+} , a rare-earth element. This broad band emission corresponds to intrinsic host lattice. These results made researchers to think in different analogy for the host lattice which exhibit luminescence and particularly in semiconducting regime that has the great potential to replace old-fashioned phosphor materials.

It is important to note that Indium belongs to the IIIA group, the group consisting of the elements like *B*, *Al*, *Ga* whose luminescent properties are already being explored [10]. Therefore, one might expect similar physical, chemical and luminescent properties for the Indium based compounds. This draws special attention towards *In* based luminescent materials, as indium possess intrinsic conductivity that is essential to prevent surface build-up charges and may also exhibits host lattice for luminescence. The luminescence properties of the rare-earth ions doped borates, aluminates and gallates have been extensively studied [10]. For example, $\text{YBO}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ has been considered as a candidate for plasma display panels (PDP) and a possible new generation of Hg free fluorescent lamps, due to their high vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) transparency and exceptional optical damage threshold [11]. $\text{InBO}_3:\text{Tb}^{3+}$ is a candidate for application in projection cathode-ray tubes. $\text{SrAl}_2\text{O}_4:\text{Dy}^{3+}$, Eu^{2+} has been regarded as good green long persisting phosphorescence [12]. The $\text{ZnGa}_2\text{O}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ and

LaGaO₃:Ln³⁺ (Ln = Eu, Tb, Dy, Tm, Sm) phosphors have potential applications in field emission display devices [13, 14]. Further, rare-earth elements also play an active role in display devices. As rare-earth elements have empty *d* and *f*-orbitals, there can be a charge transfer transitions between these empty orbitals (inter *d-f* and intra *d-d* or *f-f* band transitions) resulting in abundant emission colours. And it is interesting to note that all these transition regions falls in visible region with high purity that made remarkable position for rare-earth elements in phosphors or in modern technology applications.

Although, very limited number of studies have been reported, the following summary highlights some of the key experimental studies, their properties and approach towards application that are reported in this area of research. Liu *et al.* [15] has activated several rare earth ions at La site in LaInO₃: RE³⁺ (Sm, Tb, Pr) and observed different luminescence regions based on the dopant. All these phosphors were prepared by pechini sol-gel process as they require low temperature synthesis and also dopants can easily incorporate into host lattice. Under the excitation of short ultraviolet, they have observed orange-red (620 nm), green (510 nm) and blue-green (490 nm) luminescence respectively. These different luminescence regions observed with incorporation of different dopants because they occupy interstitial positions of different energy levels in intrinsic compound. By varying doping concentration of Eu³⁺ (a well-known red activator), Liu *et al.* [16], Tang *et al.* [17] proposed that luminescence region can be tuned in LaInO₃ and emits strong red light at 612 nm that corresponds to ⁵D₀-⁷F_J transition (J = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 usually ranging from 578 for J = 0 to 700 nm for J = 4, with ⁵D₀-⁷F₂ around 610–625 nm as the most prominent group). These emission lines have profound needed applications in lighting lamps, display devices such as FEDs, LEDs.

Several rare earth-doped LaAlO₃ or LaInO₃ have been studied as possible FED phosphors because of excellent cathodoluminescence (CL) properties. However,

LaAlO₃ has low conductivity due to its wide band gap energy (5–6 eV) [18], that is not suitable for electron disappearance under continuous electron beam excitation. So, to improve the cathodoluminescence intensity and to have better stability with high color purity Zhao *et al.* [19] has doped Tm³⁺ at La site and co-doped In³⁺ at Al site in LaAlO₃ which can be used in FEDs. When parts of Al³⁺ ions were replaced by In³⁺ ions, its conductivity will be improved due to lower band gap energy and correspondingly a blue-emitting LaAlO₃:Tm³⁺, In³⁺ phosphor was prepared by sol–gel method and its CL properties were investigated in detail. Due to the intrinsic conductivity of indium, this can be chosen as a well suitable phosphor material for low voltage (<1kV) display device applications.

In order to understand the exact mechanism behind the origin of luminescence in intrinsic LaInO₃, Lakshminarasimham *et al.* [20] reported studies on intrinsic LaInO₃, LaGaO₃ along with different doping concentrations. They have analysed the luminescence of LaInO₃ along with dopants of Bi³⁺ ions to observe the energy transfer mechanism that could improve the efficiency of phosphor. Some key points have been illustrated such as crystal structure plays a major role in characteristic luminescence of d¹⁰ ion. The excitation and emission spectrum of LaInO₃ shown in figure 1.2 has an absorption band maxima at 328 nm while its corresponding emission peaking at 426 nm with a Stokes shift of 7013 cm⁻¹. The observed broad band blue luminescence is due to strong coupling between emitting centers and host lattice.

Blasse *et al.* [21] had performed numerous experiments on luminescence materials particularly in rare-earth oxide perovskite system and reported that emission region not only depends upon the dopant but also on measurement temperature. The observed luminescence will differ and for intrinsic LaInO₃, a broad band blue luminescence is observed at room temperature along with orange emission at liquid N₂ (77K) and yellow emission at liquid He (4.2K).

Figure 1.2: Room temperature photoluminescence spectrum of LaInO₃ (a) Excitation at 328 nm and (b) Emission at 428 nm. [20]

Though, till date, very limited number of studies has been reported on luminescence properties of bulk intrinsic and doped LaInO₃ [19-21]. The dopants includes alkaline earth metals like Ca, Sr and rare-earth (RE)³⁺ elements such as Sm, Tb, Pr, Eu [13-18]. The table 1.1 gives the brief information of luminescence region with different doped materials that have been explored till date in bulk form of LaInO₃. It is worth mentioning that emission region can be tuned with temperature. The origin of luminescence in these doped materials is primarily due to charge transfer transitions between oxygen and rare earth dopants, inter (*d-f*) and intra (*f-f*) band transitions. The broad band luminescence regions observed in intrinsic material is due to strong coupling between emission centres and host lattice.

Table 1.2: Emission spectra of intrinsic and extrinsic LaInO₃ powder [8, 15, 20, 21].

Material	Dopant (x)	Emission color when Excited under UV lamp	Temperature (K)
SrIn ₂ O ₄	Eu ³⁺	Blue	RT
CaIn ₂ O ₄	Pr ³⁺	Red	RT
LaInO ₃	Pure	Blue	RT
LaInO ₃	Pure	Orange	77 (LN ₂)
LaInO ₃	Pure	Yellow	4.2 (LHe)
La _(1-x) InO ₃	0.002 Pr ³⁺	Blue-green	RT
La _(1-x) InO ₃	0.05 Tb ³⁺	Green	RT
La _(1-x) InO ₃	0.02 Sm ³⁺	Orange red	RT
La _(1-x) InO ₃	0.05 Eu ³⁺	Red	RT

RT-Room temperature

Apart from its luminescence properties, LaInO₃ bulk crystals are also driven by its possible applications as oxygen sensors, high temperature semiconductors and as an electrolyte in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC). Hongpeng *et al.* [22, 23] reported the electrical properties and structure of LaInO₃ as a function of oxygen partial pressures. Figure 1.3 shows the Raman spectra of LaInO₃ powder synthesized by high temperature solid state route. The formation of pure phase has confirmed with wavenumbers of 274 and 592 cm⁻¹ respectively. For pure LaInO₃, lattice defects may arise from intrinsic defects. These thermodynamic defects are distributed randomly so that the concentration is not sufficient to acquire high electrical conductivity which can be acquired by substituting dopants. Dopants alkaline earth elements like

Figure 1.3: Raman spectra of Sr and Zr doped at La site. (b) Spectra of pure LaInO_3 . [23]

(Lu=Sr, Mn, Zr etc.) $\text{La}_x\text{Lu}_{1-x}\text{InO}_3$. Δ that has large ionic radii may not completely replace the La ion and the difference creates large amount of oxygen vacancies (Δ)

Figure 1.4: Effect of dopants on high temperature electrical conductivity of LaInO_3 . [23]

and ultimately leads to increasing the electrical conductivity. Figure 1.4 shows the electrical conductivity of pure and doped at La, In sites in LaInO_3 increases with increase in temperature. The conductivity of doped LaInO_3 increases with increase in oxygen vacancies. By considering all the above mentioned properties and applications of LaInO_3 powder, there is in need to explore the same in its thin film form. As thin

film is not only important in any technological advancement but it will also allow us to understand the unresolved facts of this material.

1.4 Objective of the project

The objective is to make a successful attempt to fabricate thin film of LaInO_3 , a luminescent material that has never been explored by any of the researcher till date. Under this objective we also emphasize the comparison between photoluminescence (PL) properties of bulk LaInO_3 and thin films of LaInO_3 deposited on TiO_2 terminated single crystal SrTiO_3 (001) substrates by pulsed laser deposition (PLD) technique. In addition, we also aim to study the effect of different deposition oxygen partial pressure on optical properties of thin films.

1.5 Introduction to LaInO_3

Lanthanum Indium Oxide (LaInO_3) is a rare-earth oxide that belongs to ABO_3 perovskite family with orthorhombic structure. It is a wide band-gap semiconductor with bandgap of 3.7eV. Indium belongs to IIIA group along with *B*, *Al*, *Ga*. The most stable oxidation state of lanthanum is +3 and that is attained in this orthorhombic perovskite structure. Therefore, the oxidation states of oxygen and indium -2 and +3 respectively. As, both indium and lanthanum are phosphor materials and exhibits a broad band blue luminescence along with indium that possesses intrinsic conductivity finds suitable application in FEDs.

1.5.1 LaInO_3 crystal structure

The crystal structure of LaInO_3 is orthorhombically distorted perovskite type with space group belongs to *Pnma*. The tolerance factor that is calculated with the ionic radii of cations ' La^{3+} ' and ' In^{3+} ' and anion ' O^{2-} ' are 94, 117.2, and 126, respectively is 0.782. As mentioned in table 1.2, it perfectly suits with orthorhombic structure. Cations '*La*' and '*In*' occupies simple cubic (SC) and body centered cubic

Figure 1.5: Distorted orthorhombic perovskite structure of LaInO_3 . Dotted lines indicate the typical orthorhombic unit cell. [18]

(BCC) and anion 'O' occupies face-centered cubic (FCC) structure. The structure consists of indium (*In*) surrounded by six oxygen (*O*) atoms shown in figure 1.5. Out of six, four oxygen atoms are connected in one plane (along 'a-c' plane) forming a square and remaining two oxygen atoms were in its perpendicular axis (along 'b' direction). These six oxygen atoms were connected together in octahedral fashion and rare earth cation La^{3+} is in eight-fold coordination of oxide ions which have the potential to serve as a host material in phosphor applications. Dotted line in the figure 1.5 represents a single orthorhombic unit cell centred with InO_6 octahedra.

1.5.2 LaInO_3 applications

LaInO_3 has a number of applications in the various fields especially in display technology such as in

- i. Field Emission Displays (FEDs),
- ii. Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs),
- iii. Flat Panel Displays (FPDs),
- iv. Electrolyte in Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC),
- v. High temperature conductors, and
- vi. Oxygen Sensors.

1.6 Introduction to thin films

A solid material is said to be in thin film form when it is grown as a thin layer on a solid substrate by controlled condensation of the individual atomic, molecular, or ionic species either by physical process or ultra-chemical reactions. The term “thin film” is often derived from the fact that the deposited films are of the order of a few micrometres in thickness compared with the 10 to 50 micrometres for thick film. There are many deposition techniques for material formation. Since, the concern here is with thin-film deposition methods for forming layers in the thickness range of a few nano-meters to about ten micrometres, the task of classifying the techniques is made simpler by limiting the number of techniques to be considered.

1.6.1 Importance of thin films

Thin films play an important role in many branches of material science and engineering. Thin film technology is a major key to the devices since electronic solid-state devices are all based on material structures developed by the various deposition techniques.

1.6.2 Modes of thin film growth

Three different modes of thin film growth has been proposed

- i. Frank-Van der Merwe (Layer growth)
- ii. Volmer-Weber (Island growth)
- iii. Stranski-Krastanov (Layer + Island growth)

In Frank-van der Merwe mode, the adatoms fill up the terrace edges until the lower terrace is filled up and continue doing so layer by layer. In Volmer-Weber mode, the adatoms nucleate at certain spots and pile up to form dots. In Stranski-Krastanov mode, which has characteristics from both other growth modes; in the

Figure 1.6: Different modes of thin film growth [24].

beginning, a flat layer called the wetting layer starts to form, followed by bumps.

1.6.3 Thin film applications

Thin films are not confined to any particular field. It has entered in all fields of engineering ranging from electronics to mechanical, biological to drug delivery, memory storage device to integrated chips. Few of the applications are listed below.

- i. Optics: Antireflective coatings, solar cells, photosensitive coatings
- ii. Magnetics: Hard discs, SQUIDS
- iii. Electricity: Insulating/conductive films, capacitors, piezoelectric devices
- iv. Semiconductors: Integrated circuit device fabrication.
- v. Biological: Antibiotic coatings for drug delivery.

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CHAPTER 2**EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES****2.1 Overview**

This chapter presents the details of experimental techniques used in our research. Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) technique is our model system used for the growth of thin films in high vacuum environment. A brief introduction with basic principles of PLD, description of the chamber, optics and laser used are presented. The characterization techniques used were Reflection High Energy Electron Diffraction (RHEED), X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS), Photoluminescence (PL), and thickness measurement using Stylus Profilometer.

In-situ RHEED is used for monitoring and controlling the growth of thin films. AFM and FE-SEM were utilized for getting the information of thin film morphology. PL is used to study the optical properties of bulk and thin films and Stylus Profilometer is used to determine approximate thickness of thin films.

2.2 Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD)

Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) is a kind of Physical Vapour Deposition (PVD) technique. It is a thin film deposition technique in which a high energetic pulsed laser beam is used for the growth of high quality films and near stoichiometric transfer of complex compounds onto substrates. This technique was first utilized in 1960's after commercially available ruby laser was invented. But, only in the late 1980's it got attention towards researchers when Dijkkamp *et al.* [1] deposited thin film of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$, a high temperature superconducting (HTS) material that has superior quality when compared to the thin films of other techniques. Pulsed laser is used because the energy required for the ablation of material can be achieved easily.

Figure 2.1 shows the schematic of the inner view of the PLD chamber. The mechanism of the PLD, chamber are discussed in the following sub-sections.

Figure 2.1: Schematic of the inner view of PLD chamber with *in-situ* RHEED

2.2.1 Laser

The laser we used for the growth of thin films is excimer laser. Excimer lasers are special class of gas lasers in which a mixture of one of the noble gas (Ar, Kr, and Xe) and halogens (F, Cl) form the lasing medium. In normal conditions, atoms of these gases do not combine to form a molecule. But when subjected to high voltage and electric fields, excited pseudo molecules of noble gas and halogen (KrF* or ArF*) are produced. Some of them will decay to ground state emitting photons in the UV region. Under appropriate conditions, these photons stimulate other excited pseudo molecules which are in phase with the stimulating photons to form a powerful UV laser. Due to the pulsed nature of laser, the laser conditions can be readily tuned for each target. Therefore, it is possible for fabricating thin films of complex composite materials where completely different laser fluence is necessary for the deposition.

For the present work, thin films were grown by using KrF excimer laser (Coherent COMPex PRO) with wavelength of 248nm and its pulse duration is 25 ns.

The repetition rate it can vary between 1-50 Hz. The energy density of laser is maintained at $\sim 1 \text{ J/cm}^2$ and the pulsed laser is focussed to strike the solid target at an angle inclined at 45° .

2.2.2 Laser target interaction

The high energetic pulsed laser when hits the target, bright plasma plume is formed. This laser ablation process can be divided into three regimes as B, C, and D as shown in figure 2.2. The top surface layers of the solid material thermally get evaporated (regime B) with the laser interaction; a high dense plasma plume (regime C) is generated with the evaporated material interacting with the laser; an adiabatic anisotropic expansion of plume (regime D). In regime C, the evaporated materials from the target are further interacted with the high energetic incident laser. This interaction results in the formation of plasma consists of electrons, molecules and ions. The growth and quality of thin films is generally depending upon the fundamental parameters like choice of substrate, substrate temperature, deposition pressure etc.

Figure 2.2: Schematic of different phases present during ablation by ns laser: (A) unaffected target, (B) evaporated target material, (C) dense plasma absorbing laser radiation and (D) expanding plasma outer edge transparent to the laser beam. [2]

2.2.3 Laser window

Optics in PLD system plays an active role in controlling the thin film growth rate via laser energy and spot size. Laser window and convex lens are used for the laser beam to converge and to focus onto the target. By adjusting the lenses, the laser spot size and shape can be varied. When the laser hits the target, the ablated plume is directed forward and along with this, a fraction of material will be deposited on laser window. After multiple deposition of thin films, the ablated material from the target build up on laser window and starts to absorb significant fraction of incident laser energy. This reduction in energy will significantly alter the properties of thin films. Therefore the laser window needs to be cleaned periodically and properly after few depositions. [3]

2.2.4 Target carousel

Target carousel can hold six target holders which are aligned with specific distance (approx. 60°) in circular fashion and is capable of both raster scan and rotation scan for the homogeneous ablation of the material. By varying the lenses, laser energy, laser fluence can be adjusted for each target. It is an added advantage as one can load six different targets at a time and deposit either single target film or a bilayer/multilayer film using targets of their choice.

2.2.5 Substrate heater

Substrate heaters are one of the important components of any PLD system. They are regularly required for the growth of oxide perovskites that require growth temperatures of above 600°C in an oxygen environment. Three types of heating mechanisms have been used in PLD system namely resistive-type heaters, infrared (IR) type heaters and laser heating.

The substrate heater that is used in this work is a resistive-type heater. These resistive heaters utilize a thermocouple, a heating element brazed to a block. This technique is very popular for small size samples. For proper uniform heating the samples must be bonded with either silver or platinum paste to achieve very good

thermal conductivity. Thermocouple is connected with PID controller for controlled heating and cooling of heater. The maximum temperature it can hold is upto 830°C.

2.3 Reflection High Energy Electron Diffraction (RHEED)

RHEED is a versatile *in-situ* technique used for characterizing thin films during growth by pulsed laser deposition technique in ultra-high vacuum (UHV). It collects information from the surface of the monolayer. In this, a high energy electron beam with 35 keV and 1.5 Amp is directed towards the sample surface at glancing incidence angle ($<5^\circ$). The beam penetrates only few atomic layers thick and making this technique extremely surface sensitive. The crystalline surface which acts as a 2D gratings diffracts the electron beam after interacting with sample, impinge on the phosphor screen mounted opposite to the electron gun. The Ewald sphere construction in the reciprocal lattice is shown in figure 2.3. The purpose of the RHEED is to monitor and control the real time growth of the films.

Figure 2.3: 3-Dimensional view of RHEED pattern along with RHEED gun and sample stage. [4]

By monitoring the temporal evolution of the RHEED signal one can study the growth dynamics of the film. During film growth the RHEED signal shows oscillatory behaviour directly related to the growth rate. A flat and smooth surface prior to growth gives maximum signal. As growth progresses, scattering from the small 2 dimensional nucleating islands decreases the beam intensity and it shows a minimum at half monolayer coverage which is the roughest phase of the film growth. The

intensity of the beam is restored after growth of one monolayer as the surface again flattens by the coalescence of the islands shown in figure 2.4. Thus, the oscillations are a result of the periodic changes in the roughness of the growing surface and the growth rate can be deduced from the time taken for one complete oscillation of the RHEED signal. Each maximum indicates growth of one complete monolayer.

Figure 2.4: Step-by-step analysis of RHEED pattern corresponds to monolayer growth. [5]

Our PLD system at CSIR- NPL is equipped with the RHEED system that has an electron gun manufactured by STAIB Instruments (EK-35-R) capable of producing a beam having maximum energy of 35 keV and intensity of $140\mu\text{A}$ which can be focussed on to a size of $40\mu\text{m}$ with extremely small divergence of 10^{-4} radians. A double differential pumping system with small apertures for the electron beam to pass through helps in maintaining the pressure inside the source below 10^{-5} mbar. The system protrudes into the chamber to reduce the beam travel and also a mechanical alignment flange which acts as the deflection system. The diffraction pattern is obtained on a phosphor screen and a CCD camera (KF30FW) to acquire and analyse the pattern on a computer using the kSA-400 data acquisition software.

2.4 Solid state reaction synthesis of polycrystalline bulk target

Polycrystalline bulk material was synthesized by ceramic route or solid state reaction (SSR) technique. This is a general method used to prepare a large range of Oxides, Sulfides, Nitrides, and Aluminosilicates etc. Solid state reactions occur at elevated temperatures between two or more non-volatile reactants. The reaction yields a product in solid form that is structurally pure and single phase depending on the final sintering temperatures.

The reactants having small particle sizes are well mixed to maximize the contact surface area. High temperatures increase the diffusion of the cation or anion onto the specific lattice site overcoming the lattice energy. This diffusion is the rate limiting step in the reaction process. The reaction rates also depend on the contact area between the reacting solids and the rate of nucleation. Reactants having small particle sizes and similar structure will facilitate diffusion and nucleation. The temperature of the reaction is set by the Tamman's rule [6, 7] which states that the temperature of about two thirds of the melting point of the lower melting reactant is needed to have the reaction to occur in a reasonable time. The standard SSR technique involves mixing, grinding, presintering, pelletizing and sintering of the reactants until single phase product is achieved.

2.4.1 Mixing and grinding

The required amounts of commercially available La_2O_3 (Alfa Aesar: 99.99% purity) and In_2O_3 (Aldrich: 99.99% purity) were used as a starting material. Before weighing, individual La_2O_3 and In_2O_3 were preheated in oven for an hour to remove the absorbed hydroxides. Presintering removes the adsorbed gases and moisture hence facilitates homogenisation and partial reaction. Stoichiometric amounts of La_2O_3 , In_2O_3 were grounded well in mortar with a pestle in acetone medium to homogenize the mixture. The amount of material that was used to prepare 10 grams of ceramic target is calculated below.

Molecular weight of La_2O_3 : 325.82 g/mol.

Molecular weight of In_2O_3 : 277.64 g/mol.

$$\frac{1}{2} \times 325.82 + \frac{1}{2} \times 277.64 \rightarrow 301.73$$

For 10 grams of LaInO_3 ,

$$\text{La}_2\text{O}_3: \frac{162.91}{301.73} \times 10 \cong 5.3999 \text{ grams}$$

$$\text{In}_2\text{O}_3: \frac{138.82}{301.73} \times 10 \cong 4.6000 \text{ grams}$$

2.4.2 Sintering

The ground mixture is heated in the ceramic crucible with lid opened slightly in air atmosphere at 800°C for 24 hours in an electric furnace. The powder was sintered at various temperatures such as 800°C , 950°C , 1150°C with intermediate grinding. The heating and cooling of the furnace was done at the rate of 5°C per minute. The resultant powder after sintering at 1150°C was creamish in colour.

2.4.3 Pelletizing

The final powder is reground well for an hour. Few drops of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) are added into sintered powder which acts as a binder. The powder was then pressed into 1 inch diameter circular die for a pressure of pellets by using hydraulic pellet press. The pressure applied while preparing pellets is 10 tons. The creamish coloured pellets were sintered again at 1150°C in air to get dense target that was used as a PLD target to prepare thin films. The following flow chart gives the brief outline of the synthesis process by solid state reaction technique.

2.5 Thin film fabrication

Thin film fabrication by PLD technique involves several steps starting from substrate preparation, position of substrate on substrate heater, distance between target and substrate, the laser energy density, pre and post annealing. The following section gives the brief summary about the steps involved in fabrication of thin films.

2.5.1 Substrate preparation

The substrates we used for this research work are single crystal Strontium Titanate (001), Magnesium Oxide (001), Silicon (001) and Indium Tin Oxide (ITO). The substrates STO with crystal planes oriented along (001) direction were first cleaned with acetone and iso-propanol. Before etching, STO substrates were ultrasonicated in De-Ionized (DI) water for 10 minutes and then etched with 1 molar buffer solution of NH_4F : HF for 30 seconds for obtaining the TiO_2 terminated SrTiO_3 . The etched substrates were further cleaned in iso-propanol resulting in a shining surface. The substrates are then mounted on a substrate heater that can be heated up to 830°C using silver paste immediately after the etching process.

Figure 2.5: PLD System with in-situ RHEED at CSIR-NPL

The figure 2.5 shows the experimental setup for deposition of thin films using PLD.

The hints are listed below.

A- Laser port

- B- Vacuum chamber
- C- Target carousel
- D- Vacuum pump assembly
- E- Electron gun for RHEED
- F- CCD camera for RHEED
- G- Double differential pumping setup for RHEED gun
- H- Computer for data acquisition

2.5.2 Thin film fabrication procedure

Substrates were mounted on the substrate heater by using silver paste. Once the desired base vacuum of range ($\sim 10^{-6}$ mbar) is achieved, substrates were pre-annealed in oxygen rich environment at 7.4×10^{-2} mbar pressure. The heating of substrates were done in a controlled manner at 20°C per minute. The following table 2.2 gives the detailed procedure regarding the heating and cooling of the substrates that are used to fabricate thin films.

Table 2.1: Detailed deposition procedure of thin films by PLD

Heating	RT – 600°C @ 20 DPM	7.4×10^{-2} mbar O_2 pressure
	800°C – 830°C @ 10 DPM	
Annealing	@ 830°C – hold for 1.5 hours	
Deposition	@ 800°C – deposition	1×10^{-4} mbar O_2 pressure
Cooling	800°C – 400°C @ 10DPM	
		400°C – RT @ natural cooling

RT-Room Temperature

2.6 Characterization techniques

The following sub- section highlights the brief discussion regarding the techniques, their specifications and modes of operation that are used in the present research.

2.6.1 Stylus Profilometer

Profilometer is an instrument used to measure surface profile, in order to quantify its roughness. There are two types of profilometer

- i. Contact profilometer
- ii. Non-contact profilometer

In contact mode, a diamond stylus (tip) is used to measure the thickness. With the specified contact force and scan distance, the tip scans laterally across the sample surface. Profilometer can measure thickness variations in small surfaces with vertical stylus displacement as a function of position. In non-contact mode, an optical profilometer is used for providing the same information as a stylus based profilometer. They scan surfaces with optical probes that send light interference signals back to the profilometer detector via an optical fiber. There is no signal degradation along with flexibility, ruggedness and ease of incorporating into industrial processes.

In the present work, we employed AEP technology 3D contact profilometer for thickness measurement. It allows for both tip and stage scan modes. Tip scan (short scan) uses piezo drive to move the stylus upto 500x500 μm area and generates ultra-high resolution image while stage scan (Long scan) moves sample stage to generate high resolution image.

2.6.2 X-ray Diffraction

To determine the phase purity and crystal structure of LaInO_3 powder, a table top Rigaku Mini-Flex (II) equipped with copper K_α (0.15418 nm) radiation source was used. Measurement was done at room temperature to identify the phase, the unit cell dimensions, particle size determination and the crystal structure. The powder XRD data was refined using fulprof program.

The XRD for the thin films were done using PAN Analytical X'Pert PRO MRD high-resolution XRD system using $\text{CuK}_{\alpha 1}$ radiation with two bounce Ge (220)

monochromator with a parabolic multilayer mirror assembly in diffracted beam side in order to get the crystal structure, strain of the deposited films and to know the quality of the epitaxial growth.

2.6.3 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

Atomic force microscopy for the thin film samples were done at room temperature by Veeco Nanoscope Multimode V. To obtain the surface topography of the thin films, contact mode was used to scan at different areas of sizes typically ($1\mu\text{m}\times 1\mu\text{m}$, $3\mu\text{m}\times 3\mu\text{m}$, and $5\mu\text{m}\times 5\mu\text{m}$) to determine the roughness and feature size. Non-conductive silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) tips were used in contact mode and phosphorus doped silicon tips were used in tapping mode. The images were obtained by the Nanoscope V software.

2.6.4 Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM)

FE-SEM is a microscope that works with electrons (particles with negative charge). These electrons are liberated by field emission source and the object is scanned by electrons according to a zig-zag pattern. The secondary electrons emitted from the sample surface are detected in order to get topography of the sample by secondary electron detector up to a magnification of 50 kX to know the particle shape and the size distribution. The images were taken using ZEiss Evo MA10 SEM with Oxford EDAX attachment.

2.6.5 Energy Dispersive X-ray Diffraction (EDX)

When high energetic electron beam is focussed on the material, they emit characteristic x-rays. These x-rays that are emitted from the sample are collected and separated using silicon-lithium detector. The collected signals are amplified and corrected for absorption and other effects. This will lead us to study the detailed elemental composition of the compound.

2.6.6 Photoluminescence (PL)

Photoluminescence (PL) is often referred to fluorescence spectroscopy. The detection and analysis of this emission is widely used as an analytical tool due to its sensitivity, simplicity, and low cost. Sensitivity is one of the strengths of the PL technique, allowing very small quantities (nano grams) or low concentrations (parts-per-trillion) of material to be analysed. Precise quantitative concentration determinations are difficult unless the conditions can be carefully controlled. Many applications of PL are primarily qualitative. PL has gained much attention in recent years including environmental research, food and drug analysis, semiconductors and material research.

2.6.6.1 Principle of operation

In PL, a material gains energy by absorbing incident light energy at certain wavelength and promoting an electron from a low to a higher energy level. This may be described as making a transition from the ground state to an excited state of an atom or molecule, or from the valence band to the conduction band of a semiconductor crystal (electron-hole pair creation). The excited electrons occupied in higher energy levels will undergo a non-radiative transition and moves to more stable state, such as bottom of the conduction band [8]. This transition may lead to thermal vibrations in the crystal lattice (also called phonons) and gets relaxed.

Luminescence can be categorised into two types:

- i. Fluorescence and
- ii. Phosphorescence.

Fluorescence is a type of photoluminescence. It is a process in which when an electron get excited into higher energy states it will get relaxed and when reaches to its lowest energy state in conduction band, it can release energy in many ways. One of which is to return its ground state by emitting a photon. This process is called fluorescence. The lifetime of the carrier in this process is ranges between 10^{-9} to 10^{-7} seconds. The change in photon energy causes a red shift i.e., towards higher

wavelength (lower energy). This shift relative to absorption spectrum referred to as Stokes Shift.

Figure 2.6: Schematic representation of electron transitions

Phosphorescence is also a specific type of photoluminescence that related to fluorescence. Phosphorescent materials do not re-emit the radiation it absorbs immediately. Energy absorbed by a material is released slowly ($\sim 10^{-4}$ to 10 sec) in the form of light. This mechanism can be sometimes used for “glow-in-dark” materials which are radiated by exposure to light. It is often characterized as afterglow that is not observed for fluorescence. The schematic in figure 2.6 shows the electron

Figure 2.7: Edinburgh photoluminescence spectrometer at CSIR-NPL (Model: F900)

transitions at different levels.

The room temperature photoluminescence excitation and emission spectra which were recorded for the LaInO_3 powder and thin film samples deposited on different substrates like SrTiO_3 , Silicon and MgO using the Edinburgh luminescence spectrometer (Model: F900) equipped with xenon lamp in the scan range of 200-800 nm. The figure 2.7 shows the Edinburgh instrument that was installed at CSIR-NPL.

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CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The objective of the present research is to fabricate thin films of LaInO_3 by pulsed laser deposition technique. To understand the effect of nanostructures, we have also compared the optical properties of thin films with its bulk counterpart. The structure, morphology and optical properties were performed using characterization techniques such as RHEED, XRD, FE-SEM, AFM and PL. We have observed few interesting results and the same were discussed here briefly.

3.1 Bulk LaInO_3

3.1.1 X-ray Diffraction

To determine the crystal structure and phase of the LaInO_3 compound that was synthesized by high temperature solid state reaction route was examined by table top Rigaku Mini-Flex (II) X-ray diffraction unit equipped with copper K_α (0.15418 nm) radiation source. The measurement was done from 20 - 80° at step size of 0.02° . The powder XRD pattern for polycrystalline LaInO_3 powder sintered at $\sim 1150^\circ\text{C}$ was

Figure 3.1: Rietveld refined powder X-ray diffraction pattern of bulk LaInO_3 . * represent the peaks aroused from In_2O_3 phase.

refined with Rietveld refinement using Fullprof programme shown in figure 3.1 [1]. It is found that all the observed peaks are well-matched (χ^2 : 9.554) with the calculated Bragg reflections and the structure corresponds to distorted orthorhombic structure. In addition to the main phase, few low intensity peaks could be observed and correspond to In_2O_3 phase. These secondary phase peaks were marked with asterisk (*) as shown in figure 3.1. One might expect that these In_2O_3 peaks might be due to low temperature sintering. In order to overrule this presumption, we have further sintered the LaInO_3 powder at high temperature ($\sim 1400^\circ\text{C}$). Surprisingly, we didn't see any change in the XRD pattern as shown in figure 3.2. Table 3.1 gives the details of the lattice parameters of orthorhombic LaInO_3 that is obtained by rietveld refinement from the current study and literature.

Figure 3.2: XRD pattern of powder LaInO_3 sintered at different temperatures along with JCPDS data. Asterisk (*) represents peaks of In_2O_3 .

Table 3.1: Lattice parameters of LaInO_3 indicated were extracted from the rietveld refinement. Some other values obtained from the literature were also tabulated for reference.

Compound	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	Volume (Å) ³	Density	Reference
LaInO ₃	5.723	8.207	5.914	277.7726	7.31	[2]
	5.7214	8.2144	5.9319	278.7866	7.189	This work
LaInO ₃	5.7283	8.2191	5.9218	278.81	7.29	[3]
	5.7229	8.2158	5.9404	279.307	7.173	[4]

3.1.2 Field Emission-Scanning Electron Microscopy

Figure 3.3 shows the FE-SEM micrograph of LaInO_3 powder recorded at a magnification of 10 kX. The particles are observed to be irregular in shape. The average crystallite sizes of the particles are estimated to be $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$. Inset of figure 3.3 shows the FE-SEM of the LaInO_3 powder done at a magnification of 50 kX.

Figure 3.3: FE-SEM micrograph of LaInO_3 powder magnified at 10 kX. Inset shows the magnified image at a scale of 200 nm.

3.1.3 Energy Dispersive X-ray Diffraction (EDAX)

In order to estimate the composition of LaInO_3 , elemental analysis for the LaInO_3 powder have performed. As expected, the composition details obtained confirm the stoichiometric ratio of the compound.

Table 3.2: Elemental composition of bulk LaInO_3

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
N	2.56	7.76
O	25.51	67.75
In	38.69	14.32
La	33.24	10.17
Totals	100.00	100.00

Figure 3.4: EDX analysis of bulk LaInO_3 .

3.2 Thin film fabrication

The dual phase polycrystalline LaInO_3 target that was sintered at $\sim 1150^\circ\text{C}$ is used as a PLD target for the fabrication of thin films. A coherent KrF excimer laser of wavelength 248 nm, pulse duration of 25 ns is used for the fabrication of thin films.

Prior to any growth, the target is conditioned well at 10 Hz frequency to make the target surface flat. The laser energy density is maintained at $\sim 1\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. The laser repetition rate for the growth of ~ 8 and ~ 150 nm thickness films is used at 1 and 5 Hz.

3.2.1 Reflection High Energy Electron Diffraction

In-situ RHEED is equipped in the present PLD system allows us to monitor and control the real time growth of thin films. The RHEED patterns that are obtained during the growth of thin films are shown in figure 3.5. Figure 3.5 (a) shows the formation of bright blue plasma plume when a high energetic pulsed laser hits the target at an angle inclined at 45° . The plasma plume that is formed converged and directed forward towards the substrate indicating the stoichiometric transfer of compound. Prior to any processing on the substrate, the high energetic electron beam from the RHEED gun is strikes on the surface of TiO_2 terminated SrTiO_3 substrate at room temperature. The resulting Laue circles shown in figure 3.5(b) observed on the phosphor screen. Further, prior to growth of thin films, the substrates are annealed for 1 hour at 830°C in oxygen rich environment at 7.4×10^{-2} mbar. During the high

Figure 3.5 (a) observed LaInO_3 plasma plume during laser interaction with the target, (b-d) RHEED patterns of single crystal TiO_2 terminated STO (001) substrate at room temperature, prior to deposition at 800°C and after deposition of LIO thin film by PLD, respectively.

temperature annealing of substrates, oxygen ions from the substrate may get escaped and this leads to formation of oxygen vacancies. To fill these O₂ vacancies, the substrates are annealed at 7.4×10^{-2} mbar O₂ pressure. The following streaks were observed (see in figure 3.5c) indicate that the substrate surface is flat and clean and ready for deposition. Once the deposition starts, the streaks start fading out and finally disappeared completely i.e., no sign of RHEED pattern. This may indicate that the film is not grown epitaxial to the (001) orientation of the STO substrate. The results from θ - 2θ scan shown in the next section confirm the non-epitaxial growth of LaInO₃ film.

3.2.2 θ - 2θ scan

Figure 3.6 shows the XRD of LaInO₃ thin films grown on STO (001) substrate at different oxygen background pressures i.e., 1×10^{-4} and 5×10^{-2} mbar. To determine the phase and structure of the PLD grown thin films, XRD technique is used. Although, the dual phase LaInO₃ target has been used for growth of thin films, the observed peaks in the XRD pattern of thin films of LIO grown on TiO₂ terminated STO (001) correspond to the single phase orthorhombic perovskite structure with no sign of In₂O₃ peaks (see figure 3.6). The full-width half maxima (FWHM) calculated for (404) plane decreased from 0.5716 to 0.367 with the increase in oxygen pressure [5] from 1×10^{-4} to 5×10^{-2} mbar. This decrease in the FWHM and increase in the intensity of the XRD peaks confirms the improvement in the crystallinity of the LaInO₃ thin film.

As thin films of LaInO₃ might be used in display devices, growing these thin films on silicon substrate will be helpful since it is compatible to semiconductor technology process. Therefore, we have also fabricated thin films of LaInO₃ on Si (001) substrate by PLD. Figure 3.7 shows the XRD pattern of the thin films of LaInO₃ deposited on Si (001) substrate at 5×10^{-2} mbar oxygen pressure. Thin films grown on silicon substrate are observed to be polycrystalline in nature as that of the films grown

on STO substrate and in both case, most of the thin film planes are oriented in (404) direction.

Figure 3.6: θ - 2θ scan of LIO/STO thin film in the range 15 - 65° . The substrate (STO) peak is denoted by 'S' and thin film (LIO) peaks are denoted by 'F'.

Figure 3.7: θ - 2θ scan of LIO/Silicon thin film in the range 15 - 85° . The substrate (Silicon) peak is denoted by 'Si' and thin film (LIO) peaks are denoted by 'F'.

3.2.3 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

Thin films of LaInO_3 grown on STO substrate with different thickness of ~ 8 and ~ 150 nm are shown in figure 3.8. To study the surface morphology, grain sizes and roughness of the LaInO_3 thin films, they were investigated by using Veeco AFM operated in contact mode. The scan area for both 2D and 3D surface topography of the thin films are done at $1 \mu\text{m}$. The 3D surface morphology of ~ 8 and ~ 150 nm are shown in figure 3.8 (a-d). As the thickness of the deposited film increases, the grain size and surface roughness of the film is increased. The grain size is increased due to the agglomeration of particles during the growth of film on the substrate. The average

Figure 3.8: 3D and 2D topography of (a, d) ~ 8 nm (b, d) ~ 150 nm of LaInO_3 thin films deposited on TiO_2 -terminated STO (001) substrate.

surface roughness and grain sizes are estimated to be ~ 0.5 and 28 nm for the film of ~ 8 nm shown in figure 3.8 (a, d); whereas 2.2 and 60 nm for the film of ~ 150 nm shown in figure 3.8 (b, c), respectively. Figure 3.9 shows the 3D surface topography of LaInO_3 thin films that are deposited on silicon substrate deposited at 5×10^{-2} mbar O_2 pressure and 600°C . The surface topography obtained from AFM shows the thin film is grown uniform without any agglomeration on substrate.

Figure 3.9: 3D surface topography of the LaInO_3 film deposited on Silicon (001) substrate.

3.2.4 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy

To observe the surface morphology of the thin films of LaInO_3 of different thickness and different oxygen pressures FE-SEM is used. Figure 3.10 shows the FE-SEM micrographs of LaInO_3 thin films of different thickness (~ 8 , ~ 150 nm) deposited on TiO_2 terminated STO (001) substrate made by PLD technique at different oxygen background pressures (1×10^{-4} and 5×10^{-2} mbar) at a magnification of 50 kX.

As the thickness of the film increases, the particles will tend to agglomerate on the substrate. This agglomeration will lead to increase in grain size. Micrograph shown in figure 3.10(a) is ~ 150 nm thin film clearly indicates the agglomeration of particles. However, when the thin film of ~ 8 nm is grown, it is grown very uniform with the STO substrate and also without any defects or voids shown in figure 3.10(b)

A thin film that is grown at 5×10^{-2} mbar and 800°C is shown in microphotograph 3.10(c). The micrograph shows the beautiful stars like structure. Here

deposition pressure results in development of star like islands, with uneven surface and voids in the film.

Figure 3.10: FE-SEM micrographs of LaInO_3 thin films deposited on TiO_2 terminated STO (001) substrate at different conditions (a,b) ~ 150 and ~ 8 nm thickness deposited at 1×10^{-4} mbar pressure and (c) ~ 150 nm deposited at 5×10^{-2} mbar oxygen background pressure.

3.3 Photoluminescence

To study the optical properties of the LaInO_3 powder and thin films, room temperature photoluminescence studies have been performed. Figure 3.11 shows the PLE and PL of bulk LaInO_3 sample that is synthesized by high temperature solid state reaction has strong absorption band at 330 nm with the corresponding emission at 433 nm. This is similar to the results which have been reported in literature. The absorption band at 330 nm is mainly due to host lattice absorption [6] and the broad emission manifests a strong coupling between the emission centre and the host lattice. Interestingly, these PLE and PL wavelengths are close to the values reported for Bi^{3+}

doped LaInO_3 host ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 328 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 426 \text{ nm}$). The only difference observed is that intrinsic LaInO_3 has narrow absorption band when compared to Bi^{3+} doped LaInO_3 due to overlapping of their absorption bands. Similar behaviour has been observed for our intrinsic powder LaInO_3 .

Figure 3.11: PLE and PL spectra of LaInO_3 powder with maxima's at 330 and 433 nm respectively.

We have also thoroughly investigated the luminescence properties of LaInO_3 thin films grown on TiO_2 terminated STO (001) at different oxygen pressure to observe the energy transfer mechanism that will hint us to improve the efficiency of the phosphor thin film to be used in FEDs [7]. As mentioned earlier, the LaInO_3 powder demonstrates a strong blue emission band peaking at $\sim 433 \text{ nm}$ with a large Stokes shift of 7371 cm^{-1} . Figure 3.12 shows the photoluminescence excitation (PLE) and emission (PL) spectra of LaInO_3 powder, pristine STO (001) and thin films of LaInO_3 with thicknesses of ~ 8 and $\sim 150 \text{ nm}$ grown at various oxygen background pressures. Figure 3.12(a-b) shows the luminescence characteristics of both powder (LaInO_3) and substrate (STO) respectively.

Spectra from the thin films grown at different pressures are also shown in the same figure. The excitation and emission wavelengths of thin films correspond to λ_{ex}

= 252 nm and $\lambda_{em} = 412$ nm. The PL intensity of thin films has been enhanced with respect to its powder LaInO_3 and also exhibits broad band blue luminescence. This enhancement in the intensity with the application of low excitation voltage is an added advantage for the oxide display devices. As the maximum emission intensity of pristine STO under UV excitation lamp is almost nearer to powder LaInO_3 , one can easily compare emission intensity with thin films deposited on TiO_2 terminated STO substrates. The cause for the broadening observed in the PL spectra is the cumulative effect of electron-phonon coupling and size reduction of grains due to quantum confinement. However, the lattice parameters obtained by rietveld refinement are $a=5.7214$ Å, $b=8.2144$ Å and $c=5.9319$ Å. The modified lattice parameters when orthorhombic structure relates to the cubic perovskite as of STO substrate ($a'=a/\sqrt{2}$, $b'=b/2$, $c'=c/\sqrt{2}$.) [8] are $a'=4.04$ Å, $b'=4.10$ Å, $c'=4.20$ Å. Therefore, there is a lattice mis-match between the film and substrate of about 5-7%. The splitting in the PL spectra represented by arrows in figure 3.12(c) is due to the lattice mis-match between the film and substrate. But, as the thickness of the film increases, the strain in the film gets relaxed. Thus the splitting in the PL spectra reduces as shown in figure 3.12(d-e).

Figure 3.12: Room temperature PL excitation and emission spectra of (a) LIO powder, (b) pristine STO (001) substrate; and LIO thin films of (c) ~8 nm and (d) ~150 nm deposited at O_2

background pressure 1×10^{-4} mbar and 800°C . The curve (e) represents ~ 150 nm thin film deposited at 5×10^{-2} mbar and 800°C . Inset shows PL spectra of thin films grown on Si, TiO_2 terminated and as-received STO substrates.

The FE-SEM and AFM images that are obtained as shown figure 3.8 and 3.10 clearly indicate a reduction in the grain size from powder to the thin film. This size reduction towards nano led to the broadening of the PL peak in case of thin films. The calculated full-width half maxima (FWHM) for ~ 8 and ~ 150 nm thin films shown in figure 3.12(c, d) are 82 and 40 nm, respectively. This increase in FWHM also confirms the broadening of PL peak in ~ 8 nm thin films. One of the reasons behind the origin of luminescence in LaInO_3 is due to charge transfer between 2p orbital of O^{2-} and 5s orbital of In^{3+} . Moreover, +3 is the only stable oxidation state of lanthanum, which is already attained in this LaInO_3 perovskite structure and there would not be any charge transfer transition between rare-earth (La) element and oxygen.

3.3.1 Effect of pressure

The thin films of LaInO_3 grown at different oxygen background pressures are shown in figure 3.12(c-e). As the oxygen pressure during the growth of LaInO_3 thin films is kept low, oxygen vacancies will be introduced into the deposited LaInO_3 thin films [9]. For example, the thin films that are deposited at low oxygen background pressure (1×10^{-4} mbar) exhibits green PL (denoted as * in figure 3.12) at higher emission wavelength of 507 nm, which is attributed to oxygen vacancies in the system. In order to confirm the green emission observed for LaInO_3 thin film is due to the presence of oxygen vacancies or not, we have deposited another LaInO_3 thin film at high oxygen background pressure ($\sim 5 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar) by keeping all other parameters constant. As expected, the green PL peak is suppressed as shown in figure 3.12(e). This confirms that the deposition pressure also plays an active role in determining PL emission characteristics. Inset of figure 3.12 shows the PL spectra of LaInO_3 thin films grown on Si (001), TiO_2 - terminated STO and as received STO substrates at a

constant background O₂ pressure and temperature of 1×10^{-4} mbar and 800°C, respectively. Interestingly, only the thin films grown on TiO₂-terminated STO substrate showed the green PL whereas no PL peaks were observed for the thin films grown on STO and Si substrates at 507 nm. This could be due to the unsaturated dangling bonds available at the surface of the thin films as they are annealed at 800°C and low O₂ background pressures leading to required oxygen deficiencies useful for field emission applications.

3.3.2 Effect of temperature

To understand the mechanism of PL with effect of temperature, thin films of LaInO₃ that are deposited on TiO₂ terminated STO at two different temperatures (800°C and 600°C) and the same are depicted in figure 3.13. The following

Figure 3.13: PL spectra of LaInO₃ thin films on STO at different temperatures.

observation with the effect of temperature has been made. As the deposition temperature decreases from 800°C to 600°C, the PL peak has been broadened with broad band blue luminescence.

3.3.3 PL on Silicon

Figure 3.14 shows the emission spectrum of LaInO₃ thin films that are deposited on Si (001) substrate at different conditions. While comparing the PL

spectra with the films that are deposited on STO substrates, the interesting observations have been observed.

Since the lattice constants between the LaInO_3 film and substrate are almost nearer, splitting in the PL band has not observed due to less lattice mis-match between film and substrate. When thin films grown on STO substrate at 1×10^{-4} mbar oxygen pressure, green luminescence is observed owing to oxygen vacancies. However, films grown on silicon substrate at the same condition do not exhibit green luminescence. This indicates that there is absence of oxygen vacancies in the film. But, as the substrate temperature increases, similar response in the PL peak is observed such as sharpening of the peak as of in STO substrate is observed.

Figure 3.14: PL spectra of LaInO_3 thin films deposited on silicon (001) substrate at different oxygen pressures and temperatures.

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CHAPTER 4**SUMMARY**

In summary, a successful fabrication of LaInO₃ thin films have been made by pulsed laser deposition technique using dual phase LaInO₃ target that has been synthesized by high temperature solid state reaction technique. Thin films grown on different substrates such as TiO₂ terminated SrTiO₃ (001), as-received SrTiO₃ (001) and Si (001) substrates. RHEED and θ -2 θ scans of XRD pattern confirm that fabricated thin films are polycrystalline and single phase with most of the planes oriented in (404) plane. The crystallinity of thin films improves with increase in oxygen background pressure from 1×10^{-4} to 5×10^{-2} mbar.

Photoluminescence studies of powder LaInO₃, pristine SrTiO₃ and thin films grown at different oxygen background pressure and temperature by PLD have shown interesting results. The most important result was the observation of the green luminescence in films grown at low oxygen pressure. We corroborate this result to the oxygen vacancies generated during the growth of thin films deposited at 1×10^{-4} mbar O₂ pressure. Apart from its new characteristics, we have also discussed about the broadening of the PL emission peak that has been attributed to electron phonon coupling and reduction in grain size of the LaInO₃ thin films.

From morphological and optical investigations, we summarize the grain size reduces from micro to nanostructures once we move from bulk powder ($\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$) to thin films ($\sim 28\text{-}60 \text{ nm}$). It is also worth mentioning that thin film nanostructures are directly dependent on the growth parameters.

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